

**REFORMS TO ACHIEVE SUSTAINABLE RENEWABLE ENERGY
SOURCES IN UZBEKISTAN.**

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**РЕФОРМЫ ДЛЯ ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВЫХ ВОЗОБНОВЛЯЕМЫХ
ИСТОЧНИКОВ ЭНЕРГИИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.**

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**О‘ЗБЕКISTONDA BARQAROR QAYTA TIKLANUVCHI ENERGIYA
MANBALARIGA ERISHISH YO‘LIDAGI ISLOHOTLAR.**

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Abstract

It is no secret that today in every country there are various measures and reforms are being carried out to transition to a green economy and green growth. The main reasons for this are the sharp increase in the population, the decrease of natural resources from year to year, the deterioration of human behavior towards natural resources, the inability using resources in the right way, even if they are used, we can mention cases of not being able to use it at the maximum level. Therefore, many countries are trying to transition from a traditional economic system to a green economy and achieve long-term sustainable green growth.

This article focuses on large-scale of reforms aimed at green economy and sustainable green growth in our country, increasing the scale of sustainable renewable energy in our country and effective use of the existing energy system.

Абстрактный

Это не секрет, что сегодня в каждой стране проводятся различные меры и реформы по переходу к зеленой экономике и зеленому росту. Основными причинами этого являются резкий рост населения, уменьшение природных ресурсов из года в год, ухудшение отношения человека к природным ресурсам, неумение использовать ресурсы правильным образом, даже если они используются, мы можем назвать случаи невозможности использовать его на максимальном уровне. Поэтому многие страны пытаются перейти от традиционной экономической системы к «зеленой» экономике и добиться долгосрочного устойчивого «зеленого» роста.

В данной статье основное внимание уделяется масштабным реформам, направленным на зеленую экономику и устойчивый зеленый рост в нашей стране, увеличение масштабов устойчивой возобновляемой энергетики в нашей стране и эффективное использование существующей энергосистемы.

Abstrakt

Sir emaski, bugungi kunda har bir davlatda yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tish va yashil o'sish bo'yicha turli chora-tadbirlar va islohotlar amalga oshirilmoqda. Buning asosiy sabablari aholi sonining keskin ko'payishi, tabiiy resurslarning yildan-yilga kamayib borishi, insonlarning tabiiy resurslarga nisbatan xulq-atvorining yomonlashishi, resurslardan to'g'ri foydalana olmaslik, ulardan foydalanilgan taqdirda ham, shuni aytib o'tishimiz mumkin. maksimal darajada foydalana olmaslik holatlari. Shu sababli, ko'plab mamlakatlar an'anaviy iqtisodiy tizimdan yashil iqtisodiyotga o'tishga va uzoq muddatli barqaror yashil o'sishga erishishga harakat qilmoqda.

Ushbu maqolada mamlakatimizda yashil iqtisodiyot va barqaror yashil o'sishni ta'minlashga qaratilgan keng ko'lamli islohotlar, mamlakatimizda barqaror qayta tiklanadigan energiya ko'lamini oshirish va mavjud energiya tizimidan samarali foydalanishga alohida e'tibor qaratilgan.

Key words

Sustainable development, energy, renewable energy, green economy, green growth, sustainable renewable energy, natural resources.

Ключевые слова

Устойчивое развитие, энергетика, возобновляемые источники энергии, зеленая экономика, зеленый рост, устойчивые возобновляемые источники энергии, природные ресурсы.

Kalit so'zlar

Barqaror rivojlanish, energiya, qayta tiklanadigan energiya, yashil iqtisodiyot, yashil o'sish, barqaror qayta tiklanadigan energiya, tabiiy resurslar.

Introduction

Renewable energy has expanded rapidly in recent years. Worldwide renewable power capacity has increased. New investment in clean energy has expanded in every country and nations. Much of this expansion has been based on governmental support, via policy requirements, subsidies, R&D funding, or other mechanisms. Governments have promoted the use of renewable energy to address various energy and environmental issues they face such as climate change mitigation, energy security, and air pollution. As the costs of renewable energy sources have historically been higher than conventional energy sources, support policies were essential for the promotion of renewable energy. In this vein, the number and the variety of renewable energy policies have sharply increased around the world.

Like other countries Uzbekistan also have some policies and exact ways to get higher renewable energies in the next decade. For instance, one of the policies that contains the green economy, green growth and long term sustainable renewable energies is “On the measures to increase the effectiveness of the reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan to transition to a "green" economy by 2030” [1]. President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoev has signed this decision, inside it there is a conception related to the energy consumption and renewable energy. This conception has signed under the Sh. M. Mirziyoev’s decision of “On the measures to increase the effectiveness of the reforms implemented in the Republic of Uzbekistan to transition to a "green" economy by 2030” and named “Transition to a "green" economy and ensuring energy efficiency in industrial sectors conception” [2].

Literature review

Literally there are many types of renewable energy policies in history, but not all of them is supportive for the countries and authorities. Some of the policies are given in the table 1.

Country	Policy	Time of implementation
U.S	Tariff on Chinese solar panels	October, 2012

E.U	Tariff on Chinese solar panels	August, 2013
Canada	Guaranteed, long-term pricing for renewable energy from facility that contain domestic content	September, 2009
India	Requirements for solar power developers to purchase domestic products to enter into power purchase agreement	January 2010
Italy	Provision of incentive if contents are from within the EU	March, 2011
U.S	U.S. to expand solar panel tariffs after probe finds Chinese evasion	December, 2022

Table 1. Some renewable policies in history [3].

These new types of renewable energy policies conflict with the original goal of renewable energy policies because they increase the cost of renewable energy. For instance, domestic content requirement would increase the cost for renewable energy installation by interrupting developers to use low-priced imported products. Increasing trade of renewable energy products has contributed to reducing the cost of renewable energy, but it led governments to introduce the measures to protect domestic renewable energy industry, which could slow down the increasing trend of renewable energy installation. Many dispute cases have been submitted to the World Trade Organization (WTO) related to renewable energy policies as of October 10, 2016 (see table 2).

Issue	Dispute number	Respondent	Complaint	Request data
Domestic content	DS 412	Canada	Japan (USA)	Sep. 13, 2010

requirements in the feed-in tariff program			(EU)	(Sep. 24, 2010) (Sep. 27, 2010)
Domestic content requirements	DS 456	India	USA (Japan) (Australia)	Feb. 6, 2013 Feb. 13, 2013 Feb. 21, 2013
Anti-dumping measures	DS 473	Eu	Argentina (Russia) (Indonesia)	Dec. 19, 2013 (Jan. 9, 2014) (Jan. 15, 2014)
Domestic content requirements	DS 510	USA	India	Sep. 9, 2016

Table 2. Recant international trade disputes on renewable energy policy [4].

In our country, a number of priority tasks have been defined in order to achieve the efficiency of renewable energy and to reflect its weight in the country's energy efficiency. Followings they are [5]:

- Increasing electrification growth and reliability, renewal and modification of outdated electricity distribution infrastructure, increase electricity supply from 100 TWh until 2030;

- reduction of losses in electricity transmission and distribution networks, reduction of technical and commercial losses of electricity during distribution, increase the reliability and quality of electricity supply among consumers;

- Large deployment of SP resources, increasing the share of SP sources in the energy balance, ensuring the transition of the country to clean energy, development of SP resources to stimulate local industry and infrastructure development and job creation, support of local production;

- deployment of solutions in the field of energy efficiency - halving primary energy intensity in order to achieve the goal of doubling the volume of the gross domestic product in 2030 without the need for additional primary energy.

There are the main policies to get the renewable energy powers in the condition of highly demanded energies in recent ages. In recent years, the increasing demand for energy resources in economic sectors and the social sphere requires efficient and economical use of energy resources. Measures were developed to increase energy efficiency and save fuel and energy resources in large energy-consuming enterprises of economic sectors. At the same time, in the state program for the implementation of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in the "year of glorifying human value and active neighborhood", the following measures to reduce losses in industrial sectors and increase the efficiency of resource use a number of tasks have been identified as priorities, they are [7]:

- by saving 3.9 billion cubic meters of natural gas, 4 billion kWh of electricity and 21 thousand tons of oil products in industrial sectors, the task of reducing energy capacity by 20%, including 5% compared to 2022;

- task of increasing energy efficiency in buildings and structures by 30%;

- the task of increasing the efficiency of resource use and developing energy saving programs in each section of the network;

- Tasks to reduce the energy consumption (energy capacity) of the economy by 22% by 2026 by economic sectors and types of activity have been set.

Discussion and results

Understanding the economic difficulties faced by the countries of the world today and taking into account the decrease of natural resources from year to year, it is very important to pay attention to the field of renewable energy in Uzbekistan. Realizing this, the "Concept of transition to a "green" economy and ensuring energy efficiency in industrial sectors" was developed. This concept focuses on the following

chapters (see table 3) and clearly defines the priorities and tasks to be implemented for each chapter.

Table 3. Focused chapters of the concept [8].

This conception is a pathway in the sector of renewable energy for the next decades. Uzbekistan's energy production focuses on natural gas, but includes also oil and gas. Domestic production of gas is more than enough to satisfy the demand, but oil and coal are increasingly imported to cover their consumption. In 2020, the overall imports and exports were virtually on par for the first time. Fossil fuels historically account for nearly all of total energy supply (TES). Natural gas is the key energy source with 83% share of TES in 2020, followed by oil (9%) and coal (6%). The contribution of renewables (virtually all hydro) is currently modest, below 1% [9].

Inefficient energy use costs at least 4.5% of the GDP annually, with electricity generation, heating supply and buildings being important sources of energy loss. Almost 40 % of Uzbekistan's available generation capacity is past its service life leading to power outages. In the absence of policies to encourage energy efficiency and decarbonization, Uzbekistan by 2030 will find itself facing sharp reductions in oil and gas production (and exports) and increasingly reliant on coal. Research shows that potential of renewable energy sources in Uzbekistan is 270 million tons of reference fuel, which is more than three times the annual need for energy resources, and most of

this potential is in solar energy. Solar electricity costs have fallen 80% worldwide in 10 years, and are even more favorable in Uzbekistan, which enjoys plenty of sunshine.

Conception contains the following save fuel and energy resources in economic sectors in 2022-2026 target parameters (see table 4).

№	Name of the enterprise and organizations	Indicators of expected fuel and energy resource savings						
		electricity (mln kVt.s)						
		Total:	2022-2026- years	including				
				2022- y	2023- y	2024- y	2025- y	2026- y
		4 010,14	872,94	737,01	686,11	860,39	853,69	
1.	"Uzbekneftgaz" JSC	120,28	24,71	23,97	23,26	24,20	24,14	
2.	"O'ztransgaz" JSC	72,26	18,30	10,80	11,10	16,04	16,02	
3.	"Hududgazta'minot" JSC	0,44	0,15	0,08	0,07	0,07	0,07	
4.	JSC "Heat Power Stations".	686,76	129,80	91,18	79,47	194,20	192,10	
5.	"Uzkimyosanoat" JSC	63,81	13,55	13,14	12,75	12,37	12,00	
6.	"Navoi MMC" JSC	141,81	35,49	29,74	24,29	26,17	26,12	
7.	"Olmalik MMC" JSC	95,00	34,20	14,10	7,60	19,57	19,53	
8.	"Uzbekistan Metallurgical Combine" JSC	52,90	10,97	10,80	9,80	10,71	10,62	
9.	"Uzikilamchiranglimetall" JSC	0,72	0,05	0,18	0,17	0,17	0,16	
10.	"Uzavtoindusrty" JSC	24,51	7,62	4,55	4,24	4,11	3,99	
11.	"Uzbekistan Railways" JSC	2,07	0,44	0,43	0,41	0,40	0,39	
12.	"Uzeltexindustry" association	2,07	0,44	0,43	0,41	0,40	0,39	

13.	“O‘zsanoatqurilishmateriallari” association	80,40	25,20	11,40	10,00	17,50	16,30
14.	Ministry of housing and communal services (heat supply organizations)	12,60	2,52	2,52	2,52	2,52	2,52
15.	“Uzoilindustry” association	12,38	2,63	2,55	2,47	2,40	2,33
16.	“Uzbeksilkindustry” association	0,32	0,07	0,07	0,06	0,06	0,06
17.	“Uzgrainindustry” JSC	4,80	4,80				
18.	"Uzbekcoal" JSC	27,69	5,40	5,60	5,60	5,56	5,53
19.	“O‘zmaxsusmontajqurilish” JSC	19,10	4,00	3,88	3,76	3,74	3,72
20.	“National Electric Networks of Uzbekistan” JSC	47,71	10,90	9,43	9,15	9,12	9,11
21.	JSC "Territory Electric Networks"	2 364,84	487,12	472,51	458,33	474,58	472,30
22.	"Uzbekhydroenergo" JSC	1,88	0,40	0,39	0,38	0,37	0,35
23.	“Uztextileindustry” association	82,26	30,29	10,10	7,60	17,12	17,15
24.	“Uzleatherindustry” association	3,15	0,67	0,65	0,63	0,61	0,59
25.	Ministry of water management	90,36	23,22	18,52	12,02	18,40	18,20

Table 4. Save fuel and energy resources in economic sectors in 2022-2026 target parameters [10].

As can be seen from the table, priority tasks have been defined in order to achieve the desired result on the basis of specific goals in each major production network. In the implementation of these tasks, the establishment of a renewable energy source in this large industrial sector is the basis for achieving these priority tasks. For example, if we take "Uzbekistan Railways" JSC, we can see that its energy consumption has decreased by 0.39 compared to 2022. We can consider this a good result. In the process of analysis, it should be taken into account that the population of our country is increasing year by year, and the increase in the population of the country creates an additional demand for energy consumption. In such a situation, the effective use of electric energy in a state that meets the needs of the population indicates that the priority tasks set before us have been fulfilled.

Conclusion

Taking into account the climate changes and their economic and social processes in every country, the transition from the traditional economic system to the green economic system, achieving long-term sustainable development is becoming the main task of every country. Also, taking into account the changes in the climate and economic processes that are happening all over the world in our country, it is certainly a good thing that these changes are being implemented. Long-term green growth will surely pay off someday. In conclusion, after looking at several resources related to renewable energy sources and energy saving, I can say that the changes taking place in our country, specific goals, forward-looking plans will one day bear effect.

As a result of the research, I found it permissible to mention a few of my suggestions as a recommendation.

First of all, it is useful to form proposals about the establishment of renewable energy sources in which regions and information about how much money will be allocated through the open budget portal (Openbudget.uz) [11], which is emerging today as an integral part of the openness of the state budget. it won't happen. There are good and bad sides to this. On the one hand, work is carried out based on the principle

of transparency, on the other hand, it is the duty of every country to its citizens to satisfy the desire of every population for electricity. Failure to satisfy the demand of the population in a certain region and the demand of the population in another region may create a situation contrary to the rights of consumers;

Secondly, to provide more information to the population about green products and develop measures to increase their demand for these types of products. The aim is to gradually increase the consumption of ecofriendly products. It is also beneficial to create favorable conditions for the use of such renewable energy equipment, such as solar batteries, in the households.

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